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2 **An antibody cocktail targeting a Nestin-containing complex in humans with Nestin+ cancer.**

3 Pre-Clinical/Clinical/Translational/Phase1-3
4 Compassionate Use Document (FDA format)

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9 1. The formulation whose administration under Compassionate Use Protocol is requested here
10 contains monoclonal antibodies (in development) targeting each of the following molecules whose identity
11 as specific tumor vulnerabilities we recently discovered and separately described:

- 12 a. Nestin, an intermediate filament;
- 13 b. Itga7, a cell adhesion molecule;
- 14 c. Epha7, an axon guidance receptor; and
- 15 d. MCAM, a cell adhesion molecule with specific functions in traverse of the endothelium.

16 2. We include supplemental data demonstrating that black men also express very high levels of NES
17 in the primary tumor using a human solid tumor model (renal cell carcinoma [RCC]), providing sufficient
18 evidence to indicate therapeutic efficacy associated with biologic relevance and/or importance of the
19 target, pathway or network selected and further indicating that successful first-in-man testing of a Nestin
20 silencing agent will possess even greater translational value resulting from its ability to demonstrate
21 relevance associated with its basic quality and chosen method of discovery.
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2 **Nestin expression defines triple negative cancer in black women.**

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6 Breast cancer in humans is classified into several major subtypes based on tumor expression of hormone
7 receptors and the HER2+/ERBB2 enzyme (1, 2). Triple negative breast cancer (TNBC), lacking
8 expression of the estrogen receptor, progesterone receptor, and HER2, and overlapping with the PAM50
9 basal-like subtype, carries the worst outcome for breast cancer patients of any subtype (3). Within
10 patients with TNBC, disease is, on average, even more severe in black women (4). It is not yet
11 understood what disease modifiers account for this difference.

12 We conducted next generation RNA-sequencing-based whole transcriptome profiling of tumors from black
13 women and white women with triple negative breast cancer. Our systems level approach, using published
14 data (5, 6), identified nestin, a gene of neuronal origin, as among the gene products whose expression
15 most prominently distinguished the tumors of black women with triple negative breast cancer. Nestin was
16 not differentially expressed when comparing laser microdissection-captured TNBC primary tumor cells to
17 primary mammary ductal cells (7), and nestin was expressed at significantly lower levels in bulk tumors
18 from patients with basal-like breast cancer as compared to other PAM50 subtypes (8-10). Nestin
19 expression conferred stem-like characteristics and endowed cells with adhesive capacities. Higher nestin
20 tumor expression in humans with breast cancer was significantly correlated with shorter time to death
21 (overall survival). Nestin is likely a significant contributing factor to described outcome disparities in black
22 women with breast cancer in the United States. Whole transcriptome tumor or disease tissue profiling
23 based on factors that enable phenotypic stratification (in this case, race) provide critical insights into tumor
24 biology and disease pathogenesis.
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Results and Supporting Data

Multiple factors have been cited in an attempt to describe, explain or rationalize disparate outcomes when comparing white women and black women with breast cancer. African-American, or black women have been reported to be 40% more likely to die from breast cancer as compared to white women in the United States (4).

A SEER study that analyzed changes in death (mortality) from breast cancer between 1975-2011, and a separate study that evaluated trends in mortality between 1992-2009 both concluded that the decline in death witnessed among white women with breast cancer between this time period had not nearly been met in black women (13, 14).

Tumor recurrence has been reported as more rapid in black women, with shorter time to progression when comparing women of black and white race (15).

One explanation that has been offered to rationalize differences in patient outcomes based on race among women in breast cancer is that the basal subtype, the PAM50 subtype that most closely corresponds with the triple negative histological subtype (ESR-, PGR-, HER2-), and the PAM50 subtype with arguably most inferior survival outcomes, is more common in African American women than in white women (15).

It is not yet understood how and if at the transcriptional level the tumors of white and black women with triple negative breast cancer differ. Differences in tumor genetics (not differences in genetic background) among white and black women with breast cancer have been described by some. These genes include the tumor suppressor p53 and a catalytic subunit of the PI3-kinase, PIK3CA, with a reported higher p53 mutation prevalence for African Americans and a decreased PIK3CA mutation prevalence for African Americans (15).

While higher odds of p53 mutation and lower odds of PIK3CA mutation among African-American women with breast cancer were reported, the same study found that when considering patients with TNBC only, there were no differences in odds of mutation of either p53 or PIK3CA when comparing black and white women (15). A separate study challenged the assertion that p53 is more frequently mutated in African American women (16).

Race-based or race-associated genetic variation, at least some of which whose presence will likely be apparent in the final tumor transcriptome - functioning independently or in an additive and combinatorial fashion may be associated with prevalence of a more severe disease phenotype like acquisition of aggressive disease behaviors that are phenotypically apparent as characteristics like more rapid tumor recurrence when comparing black and white women. We utilized systems biological techniques, mining multiple published microarray and RNA-sequencing datasets, as well as published patient survival data, to identify genes of interest that distinguish the tumors of white and black women with TNBC, revealing important disease modifiers in human breast cancer.

Methods

We used published RNA-sequencing datasets GSE142731 (5) and GSE241876 (6) in conjunction with differential gene expression software GEO2R for this study of the influence of race on the tumor transcriptome in triple negative breast cancer. GSE142731 was generated using Illumina HiSeq 2500 (Homo sapiens) RNA-sequencing technology with $n=16$ TNBC primary tumors from women of white race and $n=19$ TNBC primary tumors from women of black race; platform GPL16791 was utilized.

GSE241876 was generated using Illumina HiSeq 4000 (Homo sapiens) technology with $n=10$ TNBC primary tumors from women of white race and $n=3$ TNBC primary tumors from women of black race; platform GPL20301 utilized. We also utilized microarray datasets GSE38959 (7), GSE158309 (8), GSE74667 (9), and GSE87049 (10) for this dataset. GSE38959 was generated using Agilent-014850

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2 Whole Human Genome Microarray 4x44K G4112F technology with $n=13$ samples of normal mammary
3 gland ductal cells and $n=30$ samples of tumor cells from patients with triple negative breast cancer;
4 analysis was performed using platform GPL4133. GSE158309 was generated using Affymetrix Human
5 Genome U133A Array technology with $n=52$ tumors from patients with basal-like breast cancer and $n=410$
6 tumors from patients with luminal A, luminal B and HER2 molecular subtypes; analysis was performed
7 using platform GPL96. GSE74667 was generated using Agilent-014850 Whole Human Genome
8 Microarray 4x44K G4112F technology with $n=23$ basal-like breast tumors and $n=72$ breast tumors of other
9 molecular subtypes (luminal A, luminal B, HER2-enriched, and normal-like); analysis was performed using
10 platform GPL6480. GSE87049 was generated using Affymetrix Human Gene 1.0 ST Array [transcript
11 (gene) version] technology with $n=14$ basal-like breast tumors and $n=109$ breast tumors of other molecular
12 subtypes (luminal A, luminal B, HER2-enriched, and normal-like); analysis was performed using platform
13 GPL6244.

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15 For Kaplan-Meier survival analysis, we used the Kaplan-Meier tool (11) for correlation of NES
16 mRNA expression levels with *overall survival* in $n=1879$ breast cancer patients, $n=431$ basal subtype
17 breast cancer patients, $n=596$ luminal A subtype breast cancer patients, $n=439$ luminal B subtype breast
18 cancer patients, $n=362$ HER2+ subtype breast cancer patients, and $n=51$ normal subtype breast cancer
19 patients.

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21 We also used datasets GSE70853 (17), GSE2375 (18), GSE84392 (19), GSE4107 (20), and
22 GSE1323 (21) for this study. GSE70853 was generated using [HG-U133_Plus_2] Affymetrix Human
23 Genome U133 Plus 2.0 Array technology with $n=2$ human tendon stem progenitor cells and $n=2$ human
24 tendon stem progenitor cells with stable nestin small hairpin RNA (shRNA) depletion; analysis was
25 performed using platform GPL570. GSE2375 was generated using [MG_U74Av2] Affymetrix Murine
26 Genome U74A Version 2 Array technology with $n=3$ mouse embryonic stem cells (mES) (R1),
27 undifferentiated and $n=6$ R1 mES cells differentiated to neurospheres for 4+8 or 4+11 days ($n=3$ each);
28 analysis was performed using platform GPL81. GSE84392 was generated using [Mouse430_2] Affymetrix
Mouse Genome 430 2.0 Array technology with $n=3$ FACS-sorted nestin- granule neuron precursors from
Nestin-CFP/Math1Cre/Ptch1-loxP cerebella and $n=4$ FACS-sorted nestin+ granule neuron precursors
from Nestin-CFP/Math1Cre/Ptch1-loxP cerebella; analysis was performed using platform GPL1261.
GSE4107 was generated using [HG-U133_Plus_2] Affymetrix Human Genome U133 Plus 2.0 Array
technology with $n=10$ control mucosa from healthy individuals and $n=12$ mucosa from humans with
early-onset colorectal cancer; analysis was performed using platform GPL570. GSE1323 was generated
using [HG-U133A] Affymetrix Human Genome U133A Array technology with $n=3$ SW480 cultured
colorectal cancer cells (primary) and $n=3$ isogenic SW620 cultured colorectal cancer cells (metastatic);
analysis was performed using platform GPL96. We also used SEEK for analysis of co-regulated gene
expression networks (22).

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30 The Benjamini and Hochberg method of p -value adjustment was used for ranking of differential
31 expression but raw p -values were used to assess statistical significance of global differential expression.
32 Log-transformation of data was auto-detected, and the NCBI generated category of platform annotation
33 was used. In the text, "% DE" refers to percent differential expression, "t" refers to a moderated
34 t-statistic, "B" refers to the log-odds of differential expression between the groups compared, "Rank" refers
35 to change in expression, transcriptome-wide, for the gene/transcript studied, out of a total transcript
36 number in each microarray or RNA-sequencing dataset, "lfcSE" refers to the standard error of log2FC or
37 logFC, "stat" refers to the Wald statistic, and "basemean" refers to the average of normalized counts
38 among all samples analyzed.

1
2 **Results**

3 Understanding fundamental drivers of tumor progression and disease pathogenesis is difficult. In
4 humans with breast cancer, race provides a unique opportunity to discover disease modifiers. Differences
5 in disease behavior between white and black women with breast cancer have been attributed to
6 differences in prevalence of the more severe triple negative breast cancer subtype in black women, rather
7 than genetic factors that confer aggressive characteristics to the tumor life cycle (e.g., tumor initiation,
8 tumor maintenance, and tumor progression [including metastasis]).

9 Here, we utilized race for unbiased discovery of disease modifiers in cancer. We performed whole
10 transcriptome tumor profiling, comparing whole transcription between the tumors of black women with
11 breast cancer and the tumors of white women with breast cancer, using next-generation RNA-sequencing
12 data (5, 6). In each of these cases, the women had been diagnosed with triple negative breast cancer.
13 Thus, our study will identify gene products (some of which will be disease modifiers) by design, that are
14 independent of the fact that black women are diagnosed with TNBC more frequently.

15 We identified the intermediate filament and
16 gene of neuronal origin nestin, encoded by *NES*, as
17 among the most significant differences in the TNBC
18 tumor transcriptome of black and white women (Figure
19 1). *NES* was the 11th most significant difference
20 across the TNBC tumor transcriptome when comparing
21 the tumors of black women with that of white women;
22 this encompassed 19,253 transcripts in total (Chart 1;
23 $p=7.32e-07$). The expression of nestin is so
24 specifically associated with neuronal tissues that its
25 regulatory sequences are used in tissue-specific
26 Cre-lox gene targeting for neuronal tissues of the
27 murine central nervous system. We validated nestin
28 differential expression in TNBC when using genetic
background as a stratifying factor using a second,
independently published RNA-sequencing dataset of
primary tumors from white and black women with triple
negative breast cancer; here, nestin was again
differentially expressed, and expressed at increased
levels in the tumors of black women with TNBC; this
trended towards statistical significance at the
transcriptome level (Chart 1; $p=7.83e-02$). On average, only approximately 11% of the TNBC tumor
transcriptome was more differentially expressed than nestin when comparing primary tumors of women
with TNBC based on race (Chart 1).

Figure 1: Nestin is differentially expressed in the primary tumors of black women with TNBC.

Chart 1: Transcriptome-wide, among women with triple negative breast cancer, nestin is among the genes whose expression most prominently distinguishes that of black women from white women.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	% DE
10763	7.32e-07	0.439	-4.952661	-2.1762315	630.34	NES	11/19,253	99.9
10763	7.83e-02	0.842	-1.76067196	-1.482899	1430.73	NES	5232/24,560	78.7

We surmised that the function of nestin in promotion of invasive behavior in human cancer could be understood in at least two ways. First, nestin expression could mark the presence of a co-regulated network of genes that function in driving migratory functions of neuronal cells. Second, nestin could directly regulate a suite, network or subset of genes involved in processes relevant to cancer and cancer progression in humans, like those involved in axon guidance and repulsion.

We began by computationally retrieving genes whose expression is most closely regulated in co-expressed networks (SEEK). We performed this analysis using datasets encompassing normal tissues as well as datasets encompassing cancer tissues. This analysis identified cell adhesion molecules integrin A7 (ITGA7) and melanoma cell adhesion molecule MCAM as the genes most significantly associated with computed nestin co-regulatory networks in normal tissues and in cancer tissues.

Figure 2: Cell adhesion molecules ITGA7 and MCAM constitute a co-regulated network of genes governed by nestin expression, in normal tissues and in cancer, respectively.

The data indicated that cell adhesion molecules existing within a co-regulated gene expression network at least partially governed by nestin were operative in cell adhesion-mediated invasiveness driven by nestin.

A cell of interest in solid tumor biology is the theoretical cancer stem cell (CSC), which might also be the tumor initiating cell (TIC). More robust tumor initiation, or a stronger stem-like (embryonic) state/transcriptional quality is one mechanism that may contribute to more aggressive disease behavior. In human breast cancer, the CSC is described to be marked by expression of CD44, and to a lesser extent, CD24 (CD24-/lo CD44+ CSC). To evaluate differences in this cellular state as an operative mechanism contributing to race-based variation in disease behavior in human breast cancer, we used published microarray data to measured changes in CD44 following small hairpin RNA (shRNA) depletion of nestin in tendon stem progenitor cells *in vitro*.

Chart 2: Nestin depletion results in loss of CD44 expression in human tendon stem progenitor cells.

GeneID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	% DE
218678_at	9.33e-07	2.07e+01	5.443368	2.64	NES	5/54,613.	99.99
217523_at	9.59e-05	9.27	2.091046	1.08	CD44	144/54,613	99.7

We desired to examine a role for nestin over CD44 control *in vivo*, and used published microarray data from a mouse model of medulloblastoma, where granule neuron precursors (GNP) were isolated from Math1-Cre/Ptc-loxP genetically engineered tumors by flow cytometry (FACS) using green-fluorescent protein (GFP) labeling of nestin, comparing whole transcription between nestin+ GNP and nestin- GNP.

Chart 3: Nestin+ tumor granule neuron precursors are enriched for CD44 expression.

GeneID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	% DE
1434376_at	0.01190525	-3.45	-2.46349	-1.10	Cd44	958/45101	97.9
1418289_at	0.00027876	-7.06	0.51685	-1.73	Nes	45/45101	99.9

Thus, *in vivo*, during tumorigenesis in the mouse brain, nestin positivity is associated with expression of the cancer stem cell marker CD44.

Invasive characteristics can be imparted to the tumor cell through a variety of mechanisms, one of which is by manipulating gene expression of cellular adhesion molecules. Cell adhesion molecules have functions relating to a variety of processes including intravasation/extravasation, axonal guidance and tissue patterning. Overall, these molecules function in invasive tumor disease behavior by imparting motile qualities to the tumor cell. We again examined cellular whole transcription, following *in vitro* depletion of nestin in tendon stem cells, using published microarray data, for changes in expression of adhesion molecules. We identified ephrin A7, encoded by EPHA7, as a factor likely contributing to nestin promotion of invasiveness.

Chart 4: Depletion of nestin *in vitro* results in loss of ephrin A7 expression in human tendon stem and progenitor cells.

GeneID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	% DE
218678_at	9.33e-07	2.07e+01	5.443368	2.64	NES	5/54,613	99.99
206852_at	4.07e-05	1.08e+01	2.847499	2.20	EPHA7	84/54,613	99.8

Ephrin A7 expression was almost completely lost following depletion of nestin (Chart 4). EPHA7 was the 84th most differentially expressed gene (out of 54,613 total transcripts whose expression was measured) following depletion of nestin in tendon stem progenitor cells. Thus, nestin likely exerts strong influence over expression of at least one cellular adhesion molecule that has functions involving migration in the nervous system.

These results demonstrated nestin control of ephrin A7 expression *in vitro* in one human stem/progenitor cell type. We examined the influence of nestin over ephrin A7 expression in second cellular context, in R1 mouse embryonic stem (ES) cells. In this model, mES cells were differentiated into the neural lineage, resulting in formation of neurospheres. We compared total transcription between undifferentiated and differentiated ES cells, using published microarray data.

Chart 5: Neural differentiation of R1 mouse embryonic stem cells into neurospheres *in vitro* results nestin positivity and gain of ephrin A7 expression.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
92905_at	1.69e-04	-5.823645	1.22724	-4.499889	Epha7	186/12482	98.5
103549_at	2.74e-03	-3.950938	-1.53416	-1.510883	Nes	921/12582	92.7

Finally, we blindly queried public expression datasets to retrieve gene expression profiles that identified differential expression of nestin indicative of some biologically relevant role for nestin function based on quantitative measures (transcriptome-wide differential expression in varied experimental contexts).

We identified transcriptome-wide differential expression of nestin in a published dataset containing tumor transcriptome data from patients with human early-onset colorectal cancer. When comparing primary tumors from patients with early-onset colorectal cancer with normal mucosa, nestin was among the gene whose expression was most elevated in primary tumors (Chart 6).

Chart 6: Nestin is differentially expressed in the primary tumors of patients with early-onset colorectal cancer.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
218678_at	8.39e-06	-5.7129791	3.72168	-1.55396803	NES	218/54,675	99.

While early-onset in human cancer is in itself described to be associated with aggressive characteristics, primary tumor differential expression of nestin does not clearly demonstrate enhanced invasiveness. Nevertheless, we identified differential expression of nestin when comparing primary and metastatic cells in *in vitro* model of metastasis in human colorectal cancer, using published microarray data to compare whole transcription in the isogenic primary and metastatic colorectal cancer cells SW480 and SW620 (Chart 7), together demonstrating nestin expression is enriched in the tumors of patients with early-onset colorectal cancer (CRC) and suggesting nestin promotes disease progression in human CRC.

Chart 7: Nestin is differentially expressed and associates with metastasis in the isogenic SW480/SW620 *in vitro* culture model of colorectal cancer metastasis.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
218678_at	2.33e-03	-4.542913	-1.6811	-0.5908168	NES	1581/22,271	92.9

Taken together, the data describe differential and increased expression of nestin in the tumors of black women with triple negative breast cancer, nestin control over molecules with functions in invasive behaviors like cellular adhesion, direct nestin influence over the cancer stem cell state, and experimental evidence demonstrating association of nestin with disease progression in solid malignancy *in vivo*.

We directly examined relationships between tumor expression of nestin and survival outcomes in human breast cancer, performing blind Kaplan-Meier survival analyses examining overall, distant metastasis-free, and recurrence-free survival in an aggregated cohort of women with breast cancer, with microarray-based tumor transcriptome and paired survival data. We examined each of these patient survival parameters in each of five PAM50 molecular subtypes: luminal A breast cancer, luminal B breast cancer, HER2+ breast cancer, basal-like breast cancer, and normal-like breast cancer. We also evaluated the presence of relationships between patient survival data and nestin primary tumor expression in all patients with breast cancer considered together, independent of molecular subtype.

Figure 3: Nestin tumor expression correlates with overall survival in basal-like breast cancer, and in all patients with breast cancer, but not in luminal A, luminal B, HER2+, or normal-like subtype breast cancer.

Top left: All patients; top center: basal-like subtype; top right: HER2+ subtype; bottom left: luminal A, bottom center: luminal B subtype; bottom right: normal-like.

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Discussion

Together, we found nestin is among the genes most differentially expressed when comparing the primary tumors of women with triple negative breast cancer based on race (black or white), that nestin regulates expression of multiple cellular adhesion molecules, including ephrin A7, MCAM and ITGA7, and that nestin exerts influence over the cancer stem cell state through control of CD44 expression. Invasive properties of nestin are not restricted to TNBC; we found differential and increased nestin expression in early-onset human colorectal cancer, and nestin association with migratory behavior could be found in an *in vitro* culture model of primary and metastatic colon cancer. In humans with breast cancer, nestin tumor expression expression correlates with overall survival in patients with basal-like breast cancer, the PAM50 molecular subtype overlapping with histological subtype triple negative breast cancer, but not in patients with luminal A, luminal B, HER2+, or normal-like breast cancer. Higher nestin expression is correlated with inferior overall survival - reduction of time to death in humans with breast cancer.

While not all disease modifiers will be viable therapeutic targets, the strong influence of nestin over the stem cell state, invasive properties conferred through migration and adhesion, and its clear influence over human survival in breast cancer deem nestin a possible but viable therapeutic target in human breast cancer. It is important to note that when evaluating nestin for therapeutic relevance in humans with breast cancer, both white and black women should be assessed as it is not yet completely understood at which point(s) (and how many points) in the tumor life cycle nestin inhibition will be relevant. We argue based on these data that thorough, adjunctive inhibition of nestin can restrict tumor aggressiveness in humans with breast cancer.

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